

TAXONOMIC STUDY OF SOME AMPHIBIANS IN BANGLADESH

M.M. Rahman, M. M. Kabir and J.K. Biswas¹

Dept. of Zoology, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka

¹Dept. of Zoology, Chittagong University, Chittagong

ABSTRACT

The research work was conducted at the laboratory of Department of Zoology, Jahangirnagar University during the period of July to December 2008 with a view to know the taxonomic parameters of some selected amphibians available in Bangladesh. The specimens were collected from different areas of the country. For convenience of observation only 4 species, *Duttaphrynus melanostictus*, *Microhyla ornata*, *Uperodon globulosus* and *Polypedates leucomystax* were selected for study. Along with some observable criteria as colour, size, longitudinal folds etc. many recognising taxonomic parameters as head length, head width, inter-orbital diameter, diameter of tympanum, distance between eye and tympanum etc. were investigated in the present study. Vomarine teeth were only present in *P. leucomystax*. Hind limbs were not overlapped in first 3 species whereas frequently overlapped in *P. leucomystax*. Tibio-tarsus articulation reached up to the tympanum in *D. melanostictus*, up to the eye in *M. ornata*, does not reach the shoulder in *U. globulosus* and reached beyond the eye in *P. leucomystax*. All the taxonomic parameters measured were more or less positively correlated with snout to vent length.

Key words: Amphibia, Taxonomic parameters.

Introduction

Amphibians are the animals with moist, hairless skin through which water can pass in and out. Nearly all amphibians live the first part of their lives in water and the second part on land, a double life reflected in the name *amphibian*, which comes from the Greek words *amphi*, meaning “both,” and *bios*, meaning “life.” Amphibians were the first animals with backbones to adapt to life on land. They are the ancestors of reptiles, which in turn gave rise to mammals and birds and descended on land from some fish like ancestors (Microsoft Encarta 2008). Amphibians appeared in the late Devonian Period, about 350 million years ago (Minelli, *et. al.*, 1987). Modern amphibians have been come on this planet for well over 100 million years; they are tough critters (Wake, 1991). Amphibians are polychromatic in nature. They are able to change skin color slightly from time to time, which help them to stimulate the opposite sex for mating. It also helps to camouflage with the habitat so that they are able to escape from enemy or adjust to the changed environment (Gadow, 1968). They are divers in color, behavior and natural history. They are found in many ecosystem and habitat, including deserts, grasslands and forests from sea level to high mountain tops (Blaustein and Wake, 1995). They cannot let their skin dry and that they thrive best in temperature regimes of 20-30°C certainly limits their geographic ranges (Duellmen and Trueb, 1986). However, more than 4,000 species of amphibians are recognized in the world, all of which are members of one of three main groups: frogs and toads (Order-Anura), salamanders (Order-Caudata), or caecilians (Order-Apoda). Amongst these three categories, frogs and toads are the most abundant in nature having more than 3,500 species and this Anuras are only visible in Bangladesh. Amphibians are important in nutrient cycling between fresh waters and upland terrestrial environments, as pond nutrients, incorporated into their larval structure, are transported to the land through dispersal and death of transformed individuals (Storer and Usinger, 1972). From the agricultural point of view they are often referred to as farmer’s Friend (Dutta and Mohanty, 1978). Frogs and Toads are economically important, as they are the major predator of insects and also for their high protein value. They are the top carnivores and major consumers of invertebrates and of other vertebrates. They are also eaten by predators such as fishes, snakes, birds, mammals (Blaustein and Wake, 1995). Thus the amphibians play an important role to equilibrate the ecosystems. At present the decline of amphibian population can have an adverse effect on the agriculture and other areas. Amphibians are under grave threat due to climate change, pollution and the emergence of deadly and infectious fungal disease, which has been linked to global warming. Many scientists have observed the diversity, ecology, economic and natural importance etc. of amphibians in different parts of the world. But only a few works have done with the taxonomy of amphibians. So, it is very important to conduct a study with a view to strictly observe the differences in various taxonomic parameters of amphibians.

Materials and Methods

The research work was conducted at the laboratory of Department of Zoology, Jahangirnagar University during the period of July to December 2008. The amphibians were collected from the bank of ponds, lakes and other water bodies and from the wet-grassy area of various parts of Bangladesh. The specimens were collected mainly in the evening to 11 pm after a period of rain. At night torchlight was used in collection for illumination. Immediately after collection, the date, time, place of collection, local name, habitat type, color, species no. and individual no. were recorded with a tag in bottle and plastic and glass zars. During the time of collections some photographs were also collected for clear justification of the study. After capturing the specimens, these were killed by chloroform and preserved in either 5-10% formalin or 30-40% alcohol.

Methods of Identification: All the collected amphibian species were identified through taxonomic keys. Among these keys the important keys are as follows-Dorsal fold, Longitudinal fold, Supra-tympanic, Dorsal color, Ventral color, Head length (HL), Head width (HW), Inter-orbital width (IOD), Diameter of tympanum (TYD), Diameter of tympanum from eye (DBET), Snout to vent length (SVL), Relative study of toe, Relative study of finger, Degree of webbing, Pupil shape, Tongue shape, Vomerine teeth, Overlapping of hind limb, Tibio-tarsus articulation, Discs of digits, Parotid gland and Warts on the body.

Methods of Data Analysis: For data analysis some statistics like measures of variability such as range, standard deviation etc. and correlation coefficient were done. Variability being a biological characteristic, no single measurement or observation of a variable is considered as an indicator of normality. A range defines the normal limits of a biological characteristic (Mahajan, 1997). Range can be measured as- $R = X_{(n)} - X_{(1)}$; $X_{(n)}$ = The lowest observation in the series and $X_{(1)}$ = The highest observation in the series (Bhuyan, 2004). To evaluate the variation of difference of an observation from the mean is by chance or real due to special reason. Actually it is used to have an idea of the precision of estimate (Bhuyan, 2004). It can be measured as-

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2}, \text{ where } \mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i.$$

The extent of degree or relationship between two sets of figures is measured through correlation coefficient as stated by Mahajan, 1997.

Result and Discussion

***Duttaphrynus melanostictus*, Common Toad (Fig. A)**

Color: All the specimens of this species were greyish dorsally and whitish ventrally (n=29), but only one exception with blackish dorsal side.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds and longitudinal folds were absent, instead of these a pair of parotid glands were present; supra-tympanic prominent; relative length of fingers were 3>4>1>2 and toes were 4>5=3>2>1; webbing pattern was rudimentary; pupil was horizontal whereas tongue was round shaped; vomerine teeth and discs on digits were absent; hind limbs were not overlapped; tibio-tarsus articulation reached up to the tympanum.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters are given below in the Table 1.

Table 1. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Duttaphrynus melanostictus*

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	53.925	± 18.3769	37.3 to 78.9
HL	18.75	± 7.51909	13.5 to 29.9
HW	15.425	± 6.48556	10.2 to 24.9
IOD	8.775	± 1.42215	6.7 mm to 9.7
TYD	4.775	± 0.85	3.5 to 5.2
DBET	1.875	± 0.263	1.5 to 2.1

NB.: SVL=Snout to vent length, HL=Head length, HW=Head width, IOD=Inter-orbital width, TYD=Diameter of tympanum, and DBET=Diameter of tympanum from eye.

All these parameters were positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.95381, HW 0.79574, IOD 0.38037, TYD 0.37819 and DBET 0.81746).

Microhyla ornata (Dumeril and Bibron, 1841) - **Ornate narrow-mouthed frog (Fig. B)**

Color: All the specimens of this species were brown dorsally with red bands and white ventrally. This result is more or less similar to Daniel, 2002. He reported 'color of dorsal skin was brown of varying shades and ventral skin was white'.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds and longitudinal folds were present; supra-tympanic was absent; relative length of fingers were 3>4>2>1 and toes were 4>3>5>2>1; pupil was horizontal whereas tongue was oval; vomerine teeth and discs on digits were absent; but Boulenger, 1890, found the tips of fingers and toes with swollen into very small discs; webbing pattern was rudimentary; hind limbs were not overlapped; these are similar to Boulenger, 1890; tibio-tarsus articulation reached up to the eye. But according to Daniel, 2002, the tibio-tarsus articulation reached to the shoulder.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters were as shown in Table 2.

These frogs were broader posteriorly whereas narrowed anteriorly. Boulenger, 1890 stated the snout as obtused.

Table 2. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Microhyla ornata*

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	21.2083	± 3.35685	17.25 to 25.2
HL	12.9833	± 1.60676	10.2 to 14.9
HW	4.95	± 0.47223	4.3 to 5.5
IOD	8.78333	± 3.04461	3.1 to 11.8
TYD	1.8	± 0.49396	1.1 to 2.6
DBET	0.76667	± 0.46762	0.1 to 1.5

NB.: SVL=Snout to vent length, HL=Head length, HW=Head width, IOD=Inter-orbital width, TYD=Diameter of tympanum, and DBET=Diameter of tympanum from eye.

Among these parameters head length and inter-orbital distance showed negative co-relation (-0.0854 and 0.208 respectively) whereas others showed positive co-relation (HW 0.95225, TYD 0.12785 and DBET 0.13654 respectively) with snout to vent length.

Uperodon globulosus (Gunther) **Balloon Frog (Fig. C)**

Color: All the specimens of this species were brown dorsally and white ventrally, similar to Daniel, 2002.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds and longitudinal folds were present; supra-tympanic was absent; relative length of fingers were 3>2>1>4 and toes were 4>3>5>2>1; webbing pattern was rudimentary; pupil was horizontal whereas tongue was oval; vomerine teeth and discs on digits were absent; hind limbs were not overlapped; tibio-tarsal articulation does not reach the shoulder. These findings were more or less similar to Daniel, 2002.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters are given in the Table 3.

Snout to vent length (SVL) was slight lesser than the record of Daniel, 2002, 75 mm. These frogs were also broader posteriorly whereas narrowed anteriorly.

Table 3. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Uperodon globulosus*.

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	55.64	± 1.95013	53.4 to 58.5
HL	11.56	± 0.6188699	10.8 to 12.5
HW	8.64	± 0.4929503	8.2 to 9.4
IOD	3.72	± 0.4147288	3.2 to 4.3
TYD	2.08	± 0.25884358	1.7 to 2.4
DBET	1.2	± 0.24494897	0.9 to 1.5

NB.: SVL=Snout to vent length, HL=Head length, HW=Head width, IOD=Inter-orbital width, TYD=Diameter of tympanum, and DBET=Diameter of tympanum from eye.

All these parameters are positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.969031, HW 0.94714, IOD 0.77154, TYD 0.69535 and DBET 0.93158).

Polypedates leucomystax (Gravenhorst, 1829) Six-lined tree frog (Fig. D)

Color: All the specimens of this species were yellowish dorsally and whitish ventrally as reported McKay, 2006.

Observations of identifying characters: Dorsal folds, longitudinal folds and supra-tympanic were present; relative length of fingers were 4>3>2>1 and toes were 4>5>3>2>1; 3/4th parts of digits were webbed similar to that of Daniel, 2002; discs of digits were present; pupil was horizontal whereas tongue was pyriform; vomerine teeth present; hind limbs were overlapped frequently; tibio-tarsus articulation reached beyond the eye.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: In order to identify the species many taxonomic parameters were measured. Some of these important parameters were as given in the Table 4.

Table 4. Measurement of different taxonomic parameters of *Polypedates leucomystax*.

Parameter	Length/Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Range (mm)
SVL	64.575	±7.12244	58.3 to 73.5
HL	20.375	± 0.78475	19.5 to 21.4
HW	18.7	± 1.3784	17.3 to 20.6
IOD	8.725	± 1.96023	7.1 to 11.3
TYD	5.2	± 0	5.2 to 5.2
DBET	2.35	± 0.057735	2.3 to 2.4

NB.: SVL=Snout to vent length, HL=Head length, HW=Head width, IOD=Inter-orbital width, TYD=Diameter of tympanum, and DBET=Diameter of tympanum from eye.

All these parameters are positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.471582, HW 0.554786, IOD 0.99684 and DBET 0.928145); but only tympanum diameter did not show any co- relation.

A. *Duttaphrynus melanostictus*

B. *Mycrohyla ornata*

C. *Uperodon globulosus*

D. *Polypedates leucomystax*

Conclusion

Recently many new amphibian species recorded in Bangladesh for the first time. It indicates we have much more amphibians than we know. This huge number of undiscovered amphibians can only be identified through taxonomic study.

References

Bhuyan, K.C. 2004. Methods of Statistics, 1st Edition, Sahitya Prokashoni, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
 Blaustein, A. R., Wake, D. B. 1995. Decline amphibian population: A global Phenomena.
 Boulenger, G.A.1890. The Fauna of British India, Including Ceylon and Burma
 Daniel, J.C. 2002. The book of Indian reptiles and Amphibians. Bombay Nat. His. Soc. Manzar Khan and Oxford University Press, Oxford House, Apollo Bunder, Mumbai 400 039.
 Daniel, R.J.R. 1991. The problem of conserving amphibians in the Western Ghats, India.
 Duellman, WE. Trueb, L. 1986. Biology of Amphibians. McGraw-Hill, New York. 670p.
 Dutta, S.K. and Mohanty-Hejmadi, P. (1978). Life history and pesticide susceptibility of embryonic stages of the Indian bull frog, *Rana tigerina* Daudin. Indian J. Exp. Biol. 16(6) : 727-729
 Gadow, H. 1968. the Cambrige natural history, Amphibian and Reptilia, Codicote, England.
 Mahajan, B.K. 1997. Methods in Biostatistics, 6th Edition, Jaypee Brothers, Medical Publishers (p) Ltd. Bangalore, India.
 Minelli, G. Giuseppe Minelli, Remo Berselli and Marzio Tamer, 1987. Amphibians (History of Life on Earth).
 Storer, T.I., Usinger, R.L., Stebbins, R.C. and Nybakken, J.W. 1972. General Zoology(5th edition), McGraw- Hall Book Company, New- york, San Francisco, U.S.A.
 Wake, B.D. 1991. Declining amphibian population, Science. Vol.253, pp. 860. Microsoft Encarta 2008.1993-2007 Microsoft Corporation.